

Project RASHealth: Water disinfection strategies to improve Atlantic salmon parr production in freshwater recirculating aquaculture systems

Deliverable D2.2

TIR on oxidative stress biomarkers in Atlantic salmon;

Date: 01/06/2022

Prepared by: Alexandros Asimakopoulos

Partners:

Funding:

Background

Oxidative stress is a condition caused by an imbalance between the production and accumulation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) in cells and tissues, and the inability of the biological systems to detoxify ROS. ROS can cause damage to the DNA and proteins, and consequently, generate break-down chemical species. In fish the effects of oxidative stress are mainly assessed through the measurement of the “protein carbonyl content”, the ratio of the total antioxidant capacity (TAC) to the reactive oxygen and nitrogen species (ROS/RNS), lipid peroxidation and the transcript and protein expression of antioxidants, while bioanalytical approaches for targeted analysis of specific biomarkers (e.g., metabolites) are scarcely reported. 8-Hydroxydeoxyguanosine (8OHdG) and dityrosine (DIY) are such specific biomarkers of DNA and protein damage from oxidative stress since their actual precursors are guanosine (nucleoside consisting of guanine and ribose) and tyrosine (amino acid), respectively. The determination of 8OHdG is reported in fish tissues and its concentrations are associated to the exposure to specific xenobiotic substance (s). For instance, the concentration of 8-OHdG in the gill cells of freshwater Van fish (*Alburnus tarichi*) increased when exposed to trace concentrations of bisphenol A (contaminant; plasticizer) for 48 hours, indicating peroxidation and genotoxicity effects. Elevated concentrations of 8OHdG in the intestine tissue of common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) were also observed under increasing hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) exposure. However, such a significant increase in 8OHdG concentrations was not documented in the other tissues (muscles, gills and liver) of the common carp. In contrast to the use of 8OHdG as a biomarker of oxidative DNA damage in fish species, DIY has not been reported as a marker for oxidative protein damage. Nonetheless, it has been extensively documented in humans that DIY is a biomarker for oxidative protein damage and it is used often as a tracer of specific human diseases.

Currently, liquid chromatography (LC) tailored to tandem mass spectrometry (MS/MS) is used to determine 8OHdG and 8-OH-dG concentrations in biological samples. Apart from chromatographic based methods, commercialized ELISA (enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay) kits are available in the market for the sole determination of either 8OHdG or 8-OH-dG. Nowadays, 8OHdG analysis in fish is mostly performed with these specific kits/antibody methods. However, the selectivity of ELISA in trace concentrations can be compromised from cross-reactivity with other co-occurring analogues, while simultaneous determination of 8OHdG and 8-OH-dG with a single assay is currently not available. Moreover, bioanalytical approaches are still lacking for the analysis of specific biological tissues such as liver and gills.

With this background, an extraction methodology tailored to UPLC[®]–ESI (electrospray)–MS/MS analysis was developed in the present study for the simultaneous determination of 8OHdG and 8-OH-dG. The method was applied in 907 tissue samples (skin, gills, dorsal fin, and liver) that were collected from Atlantic salmon parr individuals reared in an experimental recirculating aquaculture system (RAS) treated with peracetic acid. It is noteworthy that guanosine and tyrosine concentrations are altered in the plasma of salmon smolts when exposed to peracetic acid, rendering the biomonitoring of 8OHdG and 8-OH-dG as promising biomarkers of oxidative stress. Farmed Atlantic salmon is exposed to several factors that could trigger oxidative stress, including environmental parameters, water treatment, chemotherapeutics, and feed, among others. The objectives were to: (1) investigate the occurrence and concentration profiles of these two biomarkers in the tissues; and (2) establish, where possible, correlations of the biomarkers across the 4 different tissues. To our knowledge, 8OHdG and 8-OH-dG are used for the first time as biomarkers for monitoring the fish health (oxidative stress) of Atlantic salmon parr in RAS.

Material and Methods

Chemicals and materials

8OHDG was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Darmstadt, Germany). DIY was purchased from MedChemExpress (Monmouth Junction, NJ, USA). 8-hydroxy-2'-deoxyguanosine- $^{15}\text{N}_5$ ($^{15}\text{N}_5$ -8OHDG) and O,O'-Dityrosine- $^{13}\text{C}_{12}$ ($^{13}\text{C}_{12}$ -DIY) were purchased from Cambridge Isotope Laboratories, Inc (Tewsbury, MA, USA). Methanol (MeOH; HPLC grade) and water (HPLC grade) were purchased from VWR Chemicals (Oslo, Norway). Ammonium formate ($\geq 97\%$) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Darmstadt, Germany). Acetic acid (analytical grade) was purchased from VWR Chemicals (Oslo, Norway). Hybrid SPE cartridges (HybridSPE[®]-PhospholipidUltra, Supelco) and formic acid ($\geq 98\%$) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Darmsadt, Germany). The ACQUITY UPLC HSS T3 (100 \times 2.1 mm, 1.7 μm) and Kinetex C18 (30 \times 2.1 mm, 1.3 μm) column were purchased from Waters (Milford, MA, USA) and Phenomenex Inc. (Værløse, Denmark), respectively.

Sample collection

The skin, gills, dorsal fin and liver were collected from 234 Atlantic salmon parr (4 x 234 = 936 samples) at the Tromsø Aquaculture Research Station in Kårvik, Norway. The fish were 12.7 ± 1.5 cm long and weighed 29.3 ± 9.8 g (AVG \pm SD) and were maintained in a RAS during October - December 2020 [19]. Prior to sample collection, fish were humanely euthanized with an overdose of Benzoak vet (ACD Pharmaceuticals AS, Leknes, Norway). Samples (ca 2 cm x 1 cm) were dissected: the skin was collected from the dorsal region immediately below the dorsal fin, the second gill arch was used for the gills, and the ventral side was for the liver. All samples were placed in 1.5 mL polypropylene eppendorf tubes, snap frozen in dry ice and transported to the analytical laboratory frozen. All activities in this study adhered to the guidelines and protocols concerning the ethical use of animals in research according to the European Union Directive 2010/63/EU and were approved by the Norwegian Food Safety Authority (FOTS ID 24128). Limitations for analysis were registered for 29 individual samples (e.g., due to limited sample amount) out of the 936 samples (error 3 %). Thus, $N=907$ (skin: 222, gill: 232, dorsal fin: 225, liver: 228) tissue samples were eventually analyzed; all samples were stored in the darkness in a freezer at -20 °C until analysis. For method development/validation, a homogeneous fish pooled sample from all 4 matrices was prepared and stored under the same conditions as the actual samples.

Sample preparation

Extraction protocol. The tissue samples were thawed in room temperature and a portion of ~100 mg of each tissue sample was transferred into a 15 mL PP tube. Samples were fortified with 15 μ L of 1000 ng/mL isotope labeled IS-mixture followed by the addition of 600 μ L MeOH containing 1% ammonium formate (w/v). Thereafter, the samples were vortex mixed (30 s) and ultrasonication (30 min) was performed followed by centrifugation (5 min, 3500 rpm). The supernatant was collected and transferred into a new 15 mL PP tube.

Clean-up procedures. Two different cleaning methods were tailored to the extraction protocol.

In the first method (A), the extract was passed directly through a pre-washed (with 1 mL MeOH) HybridSPE[®] cartridge (30 mg, 1 mL) and was collected in a vial. Then 400 μ L water were added to the extract and the vial was transferred for UPLC[®]-MS/MS analysis.

In the second method (B), 400 μ L water were added to the obtained supernatant and were kept in the freezer at (-20 °C) for 1 h to remove any formed lipid layer(s). After centrifugation (5 min, 3500 rpm), the supernatant (extract) was transferred for UPLC[®]-MS/MS analysis.

Instrumental analysis

The chromatographic separation was carried out using an Acquity UPLC[®] I-Class system (Waters, Milford, CT, USA) coupled to a triple quadrupole mass analyser (QqQ; Xevo TQ-S) with a ZSpray ESI ion source (Waters, Milford, CT, USA). The analytical column ACQUITY UPLC HSS T3 (100 × 2.1 mm, 1.7 μm) was connected to an ULTRA C18 guard column (20 × 2.1 mm). The mobile phase was comprised of water with 0.1 % (v/v) acetic acid (A) and methanol (B). The initial mobile phase composition was 100% A, held for 1 min, and then decreased to 15% A in 2.5 min, increased to 100% A in 0.5 min and held for another 1 min, for a total run time of 5 min. The flow rate was kept at 0.2 mL/min. The temperature in the autosampler was set at 10 °C. The injection volume was 2 μL, while the column temperature was set at 40 °C. Electrospray ionization under positive ionization mode (ESI+) was used for the analysis. The MS detector settings were set at the following values: 150 °C for source temperature, 500 °C for desolvation temperature, 1000 L/h for desolvation gas flow, 150 L/h for cone gas flow, 0.15 mL/min for collision gas flow, 6 bar for nebulizer gas flow and 2.5 kV for capillary voltage.

Data analysis

UPLC[®]-MS/MS data was acquired with the MassLynx v4.1 software, while quantification processing was performed with TargetLynx (Waters, Milford, U.S.). Excel (Microsoft, 2018), SPSS Statistics (IBM, version 27), and GraphPad prism 8 (2019) were used for general descriptive statistics. Data (concentration values) were log-transformed prior to performing Spearman correlation and principal component analysis (PCA). Values below the limits of detection (LODs) were substituted with a value equal to the LOD of the respective target analyte divided by a factor of $\sqrt{2}$. Concentrations were reported as ng/g wet weight (w.w.).

Results

The detection rate % (DR %) of 8OHDG in 222 skin samples was 71%, and the concentrations ranged from <LOD to 3.60 ng/g (median: 0.29 ng/g). DIY was found in 99% of the skin samples at a concentration range of <LOD to 1518 ng/g (median: 167 ng/g). The concentration of 8OHDG in fish gills samples ranged from <LOD to 914 ng/g (median: 4.7 ng/g), while DIY was found in 99% of the gills samples ranging from <LOD to 1278 ng/g (median: 417 ng/g). Among the 225 fish dorsal fin samples, 8OHDG was detected in 202 samples with a concentration ranging from <LOD to 216 ng/g (median: 12 ng/g), and the detection rate of DIY was 78%, with a concentration ranging from <LOD to 4050 ng/g (median: 343 ng/g). Among the 228 liver samples, 8OHDG was detected in 54 samples with concentrations ranging from <LOD to 10.0 ng/g (median: <0.11 ng/g), while DIY was determined in most samples with a DR% of 97% and with a concentration ranging from <LOD to 13176 ng/g (median: 3012 ng/g).

Figures: Distribution of 8OHDG and DIY concentrations in skin, gills, dorsal fin and liver tissue from Atlantic salmon (The purple line represents median value, the up and down green line represent the 25% and 75% percentiles)

Discussion

Through PCA analysis, it was documented that there were significant differences in the concentration profiles of 8OHdG and DIY across the 4 tissues. Through Pearson correlation analysis, it was found that the concentration of DIY in skin and gill are significantly positively correlated ($r=0.338$, $p<0.01$), while the concentration of DIY in dorsal fins are negatively correlated with that in skin ($r=-0.287$, $p<0.01$) and gill ($r=-0.224$, $p<0.01$). There was no correlation between these three tissues and DIY in liver. Solely 8OHdG had a significant negative correlation between skin and liver ($r=-0.856$, $p<0.01$), and no correlation was observed between the remaining tissues. It is noteworthy to report that gills, skin, and dorsal fins are in direct contact with the external environment of the fish in contrast to the liver, and by-default, distinctly different concentration profiles among external and internal organs should be expected. The skin and gills of salmon are very sensitive to exogenously generated oxygen radicals and have the robust capability to mount strong oxidative stress response by mobilisation of antioxidants. The results introduced the possibility of using clipping of the dorsal fin as an alternative and minimally invasive approach for measuring the two biomarkers of oxidative stress in Atlantic salmon parr. Fish fins have the capacity for regeneration after clipping.

Such differences across tissues have been also previously observed for other oxidative stress biomarkers in salmon, but also other fish species. Pandey et al. (2003) assessed the oxidative stress through the monitoring of the glutathione reductase activity in the liver, stomach, and gill of the Indian freshwater fish (*Wallago attu*) across two distinctly located sites of river Yamuna (India) that maintained differences in their pollution loads. Significant differences were documented between the locations in the activity of glutathione reductase in the liver and gill of the fish, but not in the stomach tissue. In a recent study on farmed salmon, where the effects of peracetic acid were assessed, similar findings were observed; downregulation of selected genes occurred in the gills, upregulation occurred in the skin, and no substantial changes occurred in the liver.

Figure. Principal component analysis (PCA) biplot of classification of matrices based on the concentrations (UNIT) of DIY and 8OH DG.

Conclusions

The method was applied successfully in 907 fish tissue samples from Atlantic salmon, and both biomarkers were detected in most samples. The occurrence and concentration profiles of these two biomarkers were established in the examined tissues. Moreover, correlations of the biomarkers across tissues were uncovered, introducing the possibility of using dorsal fin as an alternative matrix for the minimally invasive assessment of oxidative stress in Atlantic salmon parr. To our knowledge, 8OHdG and 8-iso-PGF₂ are used for the first time as bioindicators for monitoring the oxidative stress status of Atlantic salmon parr in RAS.

Acknowledgments

Funding for this work is from the Research Council of Norway, Young Research Talent Program, project nr 302767 - Water disinfection strategies to improve Atlantic salmon parr production and the Department of Chemistry at the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU), Norway. All samples were processed and analysed at the EnviroChemistry Lab at the Department of Chemistry, NTNU.

Reference: Junjie Zhang, Eivind B. Sundfør, Rolf Klokkerengen, Susana V. Gonzalez, Vasco C. Mota, Carlo C. Lazado, Alexandros G. Asimakopoulos . Determination of the oxidative stress biomarkers of 8-hydroxydeoxyguanosine and dityrosine in gills, skin, dorsal fin, and liver tissue of Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) parr. Submitted to Journal Chromatography B.